

Report on Plants used during Pregnancy, Childbirth and Postpartum in South Kamrup, Assam

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Traditional use of native plants during pregnancy and postpartum is significant in many ethnic groups worldwide and is often closely associated with cultural beliefs of the local people. The aim of this study was to conduct a survey on the knowledge of plants used by locals of South Kamrup, Assam during pregnancy, childbirth and post-delivery period. 60 female were interviewed face to face or through focal group discussions. The main focus was to document the plants along with their vernacular names, parts used and the methods of application. The survey revealed that most of the knowledge about these herbal remedies was passed on from local healers 'ojas', rural elders and tribal folks. A total of 33 plants were recorded in the study. *Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides* and *Paederia scandens* were the most commonly used plants given to new mothers post delivery, while *Sesamum indicum nigrum* and *Carica papaya* were the popular galactogogues. Literature search revealed that the extract from peels of *Musca balbisiana colla* was found to be recorded for the first time as herbal remedy for placenta expulsion. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that provides an overview of the plant based indigenous knowledge used by the locals of South Kamrup during pregnancy and post delivery recovery period.

Keywords: medicinal plants, South Kamrup, pregnancy, postpartum, delivery.